

METHODS OF CREATING INDEPENDENT EDUCATIONAL ASSIGNMENTS FOR STUDENTS IN THE TEACHING OF PEDAGOGIC SUBJECTS

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Abstract: Pedagogical series of disciplines organization and teaching, the current situation and prospects in the development of independent educational tasks of students, the principles of the higher education system based on the advanced world experiences of higher education institutions, the learner, education recognition of lim results. The creation of the possibility of independent formation of the educational trajectory, academic mobility, and the appropriateness of the accumulation of grades are justified.

Keywords: Methodology, pedagogical features, higher education, pre-vocational primary training, organization, teaching methodology, modern teaching requirements, educational tasks, speech competence..

1 INTRODUCTION

Credit technologies, standards, curricula, job descriptions, training to ensure the effectiveness and quality of the introduction of credit technology in education, the development of independent educational tasks of students in the organization of pedagogical subjects and their teaching. principles of choosing the content of training courses, principles and methods of teaching, organization of the educational process, independent work of students (IWS) under the credit system. In official sources, the "credit concept" is interpreted as a single unit of measurement of the amount of educational work of a student teacher. One credit is equivalent to one academic hour of student classroom work per week during the academic term. Each academic hour of lecture, practical (seminar) and studio training is two contact hours (100 minutes) at the bachelor's level of the student (IWS), four contact hours (200 minutes) of the master's student (IWM) with independent work at the master's must be level¹.

Credit teaching technology is a method of organizing the educational process based on the methods of organizing pedagogical subjects and creating independent educational tasks that increase theoretical knowledge in the credit system of teaching it. can be planned separately. The essence of the credit technology of teaching is that the labor intensity of educational work is taken into account in the credits that describe the volume of the taught material. One of the

main tasks of the credit technology of education is to increase the role of independent work of students.

2 THE MAIN PART

In the modern practice of higher education institutions of Uzbekistan, various methods and methods are used to increase the efficiency of independent work of students. Among them, the following can be noted: teaching students how to work independently; formation of self-regulation of students' educational activities; encouraging independent work by demonstrating the need to master educational materials for future educational and professional activities; The purpose of introducing credit technology into the educational process of higher education institutions is: - integration of the national education system into the international educational space; - ensuring academic mobility of subjects of the educational process. IWS is one of the main resources for improving the quality of education and training future specialists. According to the credit system of education, it makes up two-thirds of the total labor intensity of the studied course. In this regard, the problem of proper and effective organization of independent work of students in the conditions of introducing the credit system of education is very urgent. Thus, the introduction of credit technology in higher educational institutions requires a radical revision of the organization of the educational process at the university, changes in teaching technology and their methodological support, independent work of students (IWS) allows you to focus on activation.

IWS is work on a specific list of topics that are allocated for independent study, provided with educational literature and recommendations, controlled

¹ Mukasheva A.K., Mustafina M.N., Shatanova R.K. Samostoyatelnaya rabota studentov v kreditnoy sisteme obucheniya <https://cyberleninka.ru/>

in the form of tests, checklists, colloquiums, abstracts, essays and reports. The entire scope of IWS should be confirmed by tasks that require the student to work independently on a daily basis. IWS hours include consultations on the most difficult curriculum issues, homework, reports, and other types of IWS tasks. The content of the student's independent work (IWS) is necessarily reflected in the work program and curriculum of the subject.

Independent work of students is a method of active and purposeful assimilation of new knowledge and skills by the student without the direct participation of teachers in the process.

Organizational measures to develop the student's ability to work independently, nurture their creative activity and initiative, as well as to ensure the normal functioning of students' independent work in general, should be based on the following conditions:

- independent work should be specific to its subject area;
- independent work should be carried out with effective, continuous monitoring and evaluation of its results.

In order to effectively organize students' independent work, a high school teacher should know and it is recommended to follow the principles of its organization:

- the principle of systematicity and consistency;
- principle of operation; principle of individual approach;
- principle of existence; the principle of appearance;
- scientifically based timing and homework dosing².

There are many classifications based on different criteria: by didactic purpose (B.P.Yesipov); on sources of knowledge (E.Y.Golant, V.P.Strezikozin); by type of tasks (M.Kharunov, I.Y.Lerner, P.Pidkassiy); by content (I.E.Cnt); multilevel classification (O.A.Nilson). Thus, the classification of types of independent work depends on the pedagogical goal, the nature of the student's activity, the type of independent work, the independent workplace of students, the degree of independence, as well as the specific characteristics of the discipline. characteristics of teaching methods and methods, specific tasks.

Methods of organizing independent work for the credit-module system and creating independent educational tasks that increase theoretical knowledge in the credit system. Activities that create the necessary

conditions and conditions for independent work, each student:

- information resources (reference books, textbooks, banks of special tasks, training programs, application software packages, etc.);
- methodological materials (instructions, manuals, workshops, workbooks, etc.);
- control materials (tests, situational tasks);
- material resources (laboratory, measuring equipment, etc.);
- time resources; consultations; the possibility of choosing an individual educational trajectory (training programs through optional subjects);
- possibility of public discussion of theoretical and/or practical results obtained independently by the student (conferences, Olympiads, competitions).

In the process of independent work, the student:

- assimilation of theoretical material on the studied subject (IWS topics, individual issues of topics, individual rules, etc.);
- strengthening knowledge of theoretical material in a practical way with the help of necessary tools (solving situational tasks, performing control work, self-tests);
- apply the acquired knowledge and practical skills to analyze the situation and develop the right solution (preparation for a group discussion, work prepared as part of a business game, "practical work", written analysis of a specific situation, project development, etc.);
- applying the acquired knowledge and skills to form one's own position, theory, model (writing a thesis, student's research work, etc.).

Assignments received by the student must be completed on time and completely.

IWS includes reproduction and creative processes in student activity and can be implemented at three levels:

1) reproductive activity (assimilation and reproduction of educational material, preparation of independent works performed according to the sample: solving problems, filling in tables, diagrams; the purpose of such work is to strengthen knowledge, skills, abilities formation);

2) reproductive and practical activity (mastery of educational material based on own experience, examination of material in practice, activity, during independent work, plan, abstracts, annotation is carried out);

3) creative activity (the student must independently choose tools and methods of work, critically evaluate the educational material and use it for effective thinking and activity, term papers and theses are performed at this level) [4].

² Lerner I. Ya. Didakticheskie osnovy metodov obucheniya. Text. / I. Ya. Lerner. – M.: Pedagogika, 1981. –186 s.

The following conditions are of great importance for the correct and effective organization of IWS:

- willingness to effectively organize independent work on the credit system of teacher training;
- the existence of a teaching-methodological complex for each subject, including a description of the course in printed and electronic form, the forms and means of monitoring the level of independent development of IWS by the student, their content and duration, the entire course for the student a guide to the training process. study period;
- availability of educational, didactic and educational materials, providing the library with the necessary literature;
- choosing the form of IWS depending on the goals and tasks of the discipline, the level of complexity and the demand for practice;
- The main goals of tasks for IWS should be clear for students, educational tasks should include elements of innovation, algorithms for their implementation;
- availability of computer and telecommunication equipment;
- IWS should be implemented taking into account the individualization of tasks, as well as the preparation and ability of each student;
- use of innovative technologies (a set of technical tools that provide students with free access to various information sources and create optimal conditions for using electronic educational tools); [3].

3 CONCLUSION

In conclusion the use of various forms of organization of IWS allows for the most effective stimulation of students' knowledge activity, the optimal load of students on independent work, the monitoring system of IWS has a personal, developmental direction and creative character, self- should be related to control, first of all, it should be necessary and useful for the student himself, implementation of interdisciplinary independent work and projects, development of social infrastructure, improvement of living and recreation conditions of students and other organizational, subjective factors are important is important. IWS can be organized on the basis of computer and information technologies, and their implementation can be carried out in the following ways: electronic textbooks, computer training programs, control programs, demonstration programs, computer models, etc.

The organization of independent work of students, especially the organization and teaching of Pedagogical subjects, the organization of training and its teaching, the current situation and prospects of teaching in the pedagogical education system in the development of independent educational tasks of students in education,

higher education recognition of the principles of educational system of pedagogy, learner, educational results based on advanced world experiences of educational institutions. It is desirable to create the possibility of independent formation of the educational trajectory and academic mobility, the accumulation of grades, the interest of professors and teachers in the field, the organization of independent education and the teaching of it, and the introduction of a clearly defined evaluation system is important..

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